

Modeling Delay in Maritime Protection Systems: From Static Barriers to Dynamic Processes

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Abstract—Maritime infrastructures such as offshore installations and ports are increasingly exposed to emerging threats, including unmanned systems and hybrid attack methods. Conventional physical protection concepts rely on the interaction of detection, delay, and intervention, typically assuming delay as a stable and predictable barrier. However, these assumptions are only partially applicable in maritime environments.

This paper examines delay mechanisms in maritime environments and shows that their effectiveness is strongly influenced by environmental conditions, operational constraints, system integration, and adversary adaptation. Based on these factors, delay is conceptualized as a time-based and context-dependent system variable and modeled as a function of multiple influencing parameters.

The results demonstrate that delay cannot be treated as a deterministic quantity but must be understood as a dynamic process with inherent variability. This has significant implications for the evaluation and design of maritime protection systems, requiring a system-level perspective that integrates delay with detection and intervention rather than relying on isolated barrier-based measures.

Index Terms—Maritime security, physical protection systems, delay modeling, critical infrastructure

I. INTRODUCTION

In the wake of the Russian war of aggression against Ukraine, there has been a significant increase in threats in the maritime domain. In particular, the use of unmanned systems and hybrid attack methods poses new challenges for the protection of maritime infrastructures [1].

Maritime infrastructures such as ports, naval bases, offshore energy installations (e.g., wind farms and converter platforms), subsea cables and pipelines are critical assets that require protection against unauthorized access and physical attacks. Many of these systems are traditionally protected by physical barriers, access control measures and spatial separation.

Recent incidents in the Black Sea have demonstrated that established protection concepts are increasingly reaching their limits. For example, attacks using unmanned underwater vehicles (UUVs), i.e., remotely operated or autonomous underwater drones, have shown that adversaries are capable of penetrating protected harbour areas undetected and reaching high-value targets such as naval vessels or critical infrastructure. In addition, subsea cables and gas pipelines have been identified as vulnerable targets for sabotage operations.

These developments highlight the structural vulnerability of maritime infrastructures and indicate that these risks are

not limited to conflict regions, but can also be transferred to other areas [2]. In particular, widely distributed and difficult-to-access offshore wind farms in the North Sea and the Baltic Sea exhibit comparable structural characteristics [3]. The combination of large spatial extent, limited physical protection and dynamic environmental conditions significantly complicates the implementation of conventional protection measures.

In contrast to airborne threats, such as attacks by unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), where physical barriers are often ineffective due to the ability to bypass them from above, maritime protection concepts rely strongly on delaying mechanisms, i.e., measures that slow down or restrict the movement of an attacker within a defined area. This makes the role of delay particularly critical in maritime security.

Physical protection systems (PPS) are fundamentally based on the interplay of detection, delay and intervention. While detection and intervention have been extensively studied, the role of delay in the maritime context has received comparatively little attention.

Delay is often implicitly understood as a static barrier whose effect is assumed to be independent of external influences. However, this assumption is only valid to a limited extent in maritime environments.

A. Problem definition

1) *Delay as part of a PPS*: The purpose of physical protection systems (PPS) is to protect safety-critical systems against threats from unauthorised persons, acts of sabotage or terrorist attacks. A PPS comprises all technical, organisational and personnel measures designed to prevent an intruder from reaching, damaging or manipulating a system. A fundamental objective is pursued here: A threat must be detected as early as possible, stopped by suitable delaying measures and neutralised within the remaining time. The three stages of a PPS can be derived from this target definition: Detection, Delay and Intervention.

Delay describes the ability of the system to physically or spatially slow down the threat. Typical elements of a delay in a land-based PPS can be: physical barriers (fences, gates, perimeter barriers), access control systems, structural obstacles (e.g. platform railings, technical enclosures) and natural obstacles (tree lines, rivers). The aim of the delay is to

delay the threat for as long as possible so that the intervention can take effect in good time.

2) *Delay in maritime environments:* In the maritime scenarios, a rethinking of the classic barriers is required, as they differ significantly from the land area. In the surface area, spatial factors such as distance, approach corridors or obstacle fields (crossing a wind turbine field) play a major role. Historically, barrage balloons, fog launchers and ships or physical objects (sometimes grounded) were used in this category. Underwater, on the other hand, physical barriers can be used. Examples include net barriers, anti-submarine nets, massive iron chains, minefields and floating barriers.

3) *Research requirements:* Existing research in the field of physical protection systems focusses mainly on detection and intervention mechanisms. Delay is often only considered as a supporting factor and is not systematically analysed. For maritime scenarios in particular, there is a lack of structured consideration of the influencing factors and their effects on the effectiveness of delay mechanisms.

4) *Objective:* The aim of this paper is to systematically analyse the role of delay in maritime environments and to develop a conceptual model to assess the effectiveness of delay mechanisms. To this end, relevant delay mechanisms are first identified and their challenges analysed. After that, a time-based model is developed that describes delay as a dynamic and context-dependent system variable.

II. APPLICATION IN A HISTORICAL CONTEXT

Delay mechanisms have been used in a variety of ways in maritime history to control access to ports and critical infrastructure. Both punctual barriers such as chains and net systems as well as large-scale blockade concepts were used.

An early example is the Ottoman siege of Constantinople in 1453. A massive iron chain blocked the entrance to the protected harbour bay and initially prevented the fleet from entering. However, this measure showed that delay alone does not guarantee complete protection: The barrier was circumvented by transporting ships overland. [4] This example illustrates that delaying measures can be overcome through adaptation by the attacker.

Maritime barriers such as net barriers and blockade systems were also used in the 20th century, particularly to protect ports and naval bases against submarines. During the attack on the British naval base at Scapa Flow in 1939, the German submarine U 47 was able to enter the harbour despite the existing barriers. The main reasons for this were changing environmental conditions, ageing processes of the barriers used and misjudgements regarding their actual effectiveness. [5]

Both examples show that maritime delay mechanisms cannot be understood as static and permanently effective barriers. Rather, their effectiveness is subject to continuous change and is heavily dependent on external influences and the behaviour of the attacker. Delay must therefore be understood historically as a dynamic and context-dependent process.

A. Possible application scenarios today

Basic categories of modern delay mechanisms can be derived from the historical examples, which can also be used in today's maritime scenarios:

- **Fog systems:** Short-term impairment of visibility and optical systems, especially for drone-based attacks, but highly dependent on weather conditions.
- **Ships/physical blockades:** Blocking of access routes or sea areas, but with high resource requirements and limited durability.
- **Net blockades and anti-submarine nets:** Delaying underwater threats, but susceptible to environmental and ageing influences.
- **Floating barriers:** Flexible, floating barrier systems for defence against surface and partially underwater threats, but highly dependent on environmental conditions and structural integrity.
- **Locks:** Controlled access points with a high level of protection, but which can themselves act as critical weak points.
- **Minefields:** Effective area denial, but with significant operational, legal and security limitations.

III. CHALLENGES

The effectiveness of delay mechanisms in maritime areas is determined by a large number of factors. These include, in particular, environmental conditions, operational boundary conditions and integration into the overall system. In contrast to land-based protection systems, in the maritime environment these factors often act simultaneously and lead to complex interactions. Delay should therefore not be understood as an isolated characteristic of individual measures, but rather as the result of a dynamic interplay between various system components. Environmental conditions such as swell, currents or visibility can change at short notice and directly influence the effectiveness of barriers. At the same time, operational requirements, such as maintenance windows or necessary access, mean that delay measures are not always fully operational and effective. Delay mechanisms are only effective in conjunction with detection and intervention processes, whereby a lack of or insufficient integration can lead to attack delays caused by barriers not being utilised effectively. Another key influencing factor is the attacker's ability to adapt. Instead of overcoming existing barriers directly, alternative attack routes can be used or vulnerabilities can be exploited in a targeted manner. This leads to a continuous shift of vulnerabilities within the system. Overall, the result is that maritime delay mechanisms and effects are characterised by a high degree of variability, uncertainty and context dependency. A purely static view of individual measures is therefore not sufficient to map and measure protection effect. The various influencing factors and their impact on the delay effects are systematically summarised in Table I.

TABLE I
CHALLENGES AFFECTING DELAY IN MARITIME PROTECTION SYSTEMS

Category	Characteristics	Impact
Environmental & natural conditions	State of the sea, tides, storm Sediment transport Biofouling	Effectiveness decreases over time Increased maintenance requirements Uncertain barrier effectiveness
Maintenance, operation and lifecycle	Regular inspections required (ROV/divers) Weather windows limit access Material fatigue difficult to detect Spare parts & logistics at sea complex	Effectiveness not constant Installed \neq available Gradual vulnerability
Environmental & regulatory issues	Protected areas (e.g., Wadden Sea) Impact on marine mammals, fish and bird migration Environmental impact assessments Lengthy approval processes	Limited applicability Technically feasible \neq legally permissible Limited design options (depth, material, duration)
Nautical & operational	Proximity to shipping routes Service & emergency access Collision risk for civilian vessels	No full-area coverage Required openings \rightarrow vulnerabilities Dependence on operational states
Adaptability of the adversary	Adversaries learn barrier configurations Circumvention instead of penetration Exploitation of exceptional situations Use of alternative attack vectors	Decreasing effectiveness over time Shift of the worst path Predictable vulnerabilities
Technical & systemic	Barriers without sensors are blind Lack of integration with detection & intervention Individual barriers create a false sense of security	Time gain remains unused Disruption of the PPS chain High investment with low effectiveness
Cost & scalability	High installation costs High OPEX Limited scalability for large areas Economically difficult to justify	Focus on high-value assets Only partial coverage Trade-off between cost and protection effectiveness

IV. DESIGN MODEL

The challenges presented in Section III make it clear that delay mechanisms in the maritime environments are characterised by a high degree of dynamism, uncertainty and context dependency. A purely qualitative consideration of these influencing factors is therefore not sufficient to systematically assess the actual effectiveness of delay.

Against this background, a conceptual model is developed below that describes delay as a time-based and context-dependent system variable.

A. Conceptualisation of Delay as a Time-Based Metric

Delay is modelled as a time-based system metric for the structured evaluation of delay mechanisms. This approach is based on established concepts of physical protection systems, in which the effectiveness of a protection system along attack paths is described by a time-based interaction of detection, delay and intervention [6].

In such models, the progress of an attacker along an attack path is described by the time required to overcome barriers and cross protected areas. At the same time, the ability of the protection system to detect and stop an attacker within a certain reaction time is considered [6].

Two central variables are introduced to conceptually describe this relationship: the delay time T_d and the intervention time T_i . T_d describes the time it takes an attacker to reach a target, while T_i is the time it takes for countermeasures to successfully intervene.

The effectiveness of a defence system therefore results from the ratio of these two variables. A successful defence is given

if the delay time exceeds the required intervention time, i.e. if $T_d > T_i$ applies.

In contrast to existing work, this article considers delay mechanisms and effects in isolation and develops it further specifically in a maritime context.

B. Influence Factors and Variability of Delay

The influencing factors identified in Section III have a direct effect on the delay time T_d and determine its level, stability and availability in operational use.

While in existing models delay along an attack path is often assumed to be a deterministic or can at least be described as a stable variable [6], this assumption is only valid to a limited extent in a maritime context. The effectiveness of delay mechanisms is subject to considerable fluctuations and can change both spatially and temporally.

For the conceptual description, the delay time is therefore not modelled as a fixed value, but as a function of several influencing factors:

$$T_d = f(E, B, S, A) \quad (1)$$

where E represents environmental conditions, B operational conditions, S system integration and A the behaviour of the attacker.

In contrast to classical approaches, this means that identical delay measures do not lead to a reproducible time gain. Instead, T_d can vary or be temporarily reduced depending on the scenario, system status and external conditions.

The evaluation of delay therefore requires a context-dependent approach in which, in addition to the nominal time

gain, its variability and reliability in particular must be taken into account.

C. Implications for the Evaluation of Delay

The previous modelling shows that delay in the maritime context cannot be assessed as a deterministic variable. Instead, the delay time T_d must be regarded as variable and scenario-dependent.

For the evaluation of protection systems, this means that it is not only the nominal time gain that is decisive, but in particular its reliability and stability under different conditions. An isolated consideration of individual delay measures is not sufficient, as their effectiveness depends significantly on the interaction with detection and intervention processes.

A suitable assessment therefore requires a systemic perspective in which delay is understood as part of a networked protection chain. Against this background, it makes sense to interpret delay conceptually as an uncertain or distributed variable, the extent of which depends on the respective scenario and the underlying influencing factors.

This makes it clear that the design of maritime protection systems cannot be based on static barriers, but that an adaptive and context-dependent view of delay is required.

D. Example Application of the Model

To illustrate this, the conceptual model is applied to a simplified scenario. An offshore wind farm that is attacked by unmanned surface vessels (USVs) is considered. In this case, the delay does not result from classic barriers, but from spatial factors such as the distance to the target and the need to cross the wind turbine field.

Under ideal conditions, the delay time T_d can be sufficiently long to allow timely intervention. However, changing environmental conditions, such as increased sea conditions or limited visibility, as well as operational restrictions, can lead to a significant reduction in T_d . At the same time, the intervention time T_i remains largely constant in many cases or even increases due to more difficult operating conditions.

The model makes it clear that the effectiveness of the delay depends heavily on the respective scenario. An isolated consideration of individual measures is therefore not sufficient to reliably evaluate the protective effect. Instead, a context-dependent analysis is required in which the variability of T_d is taken into account.

V. DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The model shows that the effectiveness of delay in maritime environments cannot be considered in isolation. Delay is only effective in conjunction with detection and intervention and must therefore be understood as an integral part of a networked protection chain.

In practical terms, this implies that the evaluation of maritime protection systems cannot rely on fixed assumptions about delay performance. Instead, it requires scenario-based assessments that explicitly consider environmental variability, operational constraints and system dependencies.

Furthermore, the results indicate that increasing the robustness of delay mechanisms alone is not sufficient to improve overall system effectiveness. Rather, the coordination between detection, delay and intervention becomes the critical factor. Delays that cannot be reliably detected or exploited by response forces do not contribute to effective protection.

From a system design perspective, this suggests that future maritime protection concepts should focus on integrated solutions that combine sensor systems, communication structures and response capabilities. In particular, the dynamic nature of maritime environments requires adaptive strategies that can respond to changing conditions and evolving attack patterns in real time.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has shown that delay mechanisms in the maritime context are subject to fundamentally different framework conditions than in land-based protection systems. The analysis of the influencing factors makes it clear that delay should not be understood as a static barrier, but rather as a dynamic and context-dependent process.

By introducing a conceptual model based on the delay time and the intervention time, it was possible to develop a structured view of the effectiveness of delay in maritime areas. This approach demonstrates that the evaluation of protection systems cannot be based on fixed time assumptions, but must take the variability and uncertainty of delay effects into account.

The results suggest that future protection concepts should focus more on systemic integration and adaptive approaches. Further work can build on this to develop quantitative models or simulation-based approaches for evaluating maritime protection systems.

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